

Effect of Good Governance Application against Public Satisfaction with Excellent Service as an Intervening Variable in the Medan Tembung Sub-District Office

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the influence of good governance against public satisfaction mediated by the excellent service of Medan Tembung Sub-District employees. The data in this study were obtained from the results of filling out the questionnaire by 100 respondents who were all residents who received services in Medan Tembung Sub-District. The result of data subsequent studies were analyzed both descriptively and quantitatively to find a picture of good governance, excellent service and public satisfaction that received services in Medan Tembung Sub-District and to determine the influence of good governance against public satisfaction mediated by the excellent service of Medan Tembung Sub-District employees. Descriptive analysis was carried out by looking at the average value of each indicator of the research variable, while the quantitative analysis was carried out using PLS analysis techniques with the help of the SmartPLS 3 version programme. Based on the results of the PLS analysis, the analysis shows that directly, good governance can influence against public satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.518, in addition, this variable also has a significant influence against excellent service variable with a path coefficient of 0.454 and excellent service variables can influence against public satisfaction with a path coefficient of 0.496. Based on this relationship, in general it can be concluded that in addition to directly affecting public satisfaction, good governance can also indirectly influence public satisfaction by being mediated by excellent service variables.

Keywords: Good Governance, Excellent Service, Public Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Public welfare can be measured by how much the level of public satisfaction has been felt for public services that have been provided by government officials. According to Ridwan and Sudrajat (2009:19) public service is a service provided by the government as a state organizer for its people to meet the needs of the community itself and has the aim to improve the welfare of the community. While public satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure that is felt by the community for what has been obtained by the community. Meanwhile, according to Kotler and Keller (2009:138) what defines satisfaction is someone's pleasure or disappointment that arises because of comparing the perceived performance of the product (or results) against their expectations. If the services provided do not meet expectations, the public will not feel satisfied, and if the services provided are in accordance with expectations, then the public will feel satisfied. So that the public can feel the results of comparisons of services received by a government apparatus demanded to provide the best possible service to the public.

Based on the results of the pre-survey research, it was concluded that Medan Tembung Subdistrict was good in terms of providing convenience in service

flow procedures and services provided equitably, but there were still two issues that had to be addressed by the Medan Tembung Subdistrict so that the community was not satisfied, namely the condition of facilities and infrastructure which is inadequate like a hot service process place because the service location is not covered by a roof so that during the day it will feel hot plus the lack of seats in the service place so that people feel uncomfortable because someone has to stand up, and another problem is the problem of improper document settlement time, one of the reasons the community assesses that the completion time is not timely, because there is no certainty from the employees over the completion of documents that are managed by the people who are dealing in Medan Tembung Sub-District Office.

Based on the results of the pre-survey research it can be concluded that the services provided by Medan Tembung Sub-District Office employees are good, such as employees in Medan Tembung Sub-District Office are always ready to serve the community who are dealing in Medan Tembung District and serious employees listen to every question of each service requestor, but there are also those who be a concern and must be addressed by employees so that more excellent services can be realized that employees must be cheaper to smile when serving each service requestor then who should be attentive and must be addressed by other employees that is to say thank you when finished providing services to each service requester, thus the community will feel served as well as possible. According to LAN-RI 2004, Excellent Service is a very good service and/or best service, in accordance with applicable standards or those of the agencies that provide services so that they are able to satisfy the parties served (the public).

The concept of good governance through public services was difficult to realize when they did not have the authority and responsibility to make their own decisions in order to regulate and manage

the interests of the community according to their own initiatives based on the aspirations of the local people in accordance with the conditions, potential, and characteristics they have. The authority and responsibility to make their own decisions are often referred to as decentralization, so the question of Good Governance cannot be separated from the problem of decentralization (Fitriani, 2017:325).

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Good Governance

The application of the principles of good governance is very important in the implementation of public services to improve the performance of the state apparatus. This is because the government designed the concepts of good governance principles to increase the potential for changes in the bureaucracy in order to create better public services, besides that the public still considered the public services carried out by the bureaucracy would definitely be slow, unprofessional, and expensive. fat and authority among institutions that overlap, systems, methods, and procedures have not been disciplined, civil servants are not professional, not yet neutral and prosperous, corrupt practices, collusion and nepotism are still rooted, coordination, integration, and synchronization of programs have not been directed, and discipline and ethos state employment is still low.

According to Mas'ood (2003) in Santosa (2008:55) good governance is a principle in regulating governance that enables efficient public services, a reliable court system and its accountability is accountable to the public.

2.1.1 Principles of Good Governance

According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) as a body/institution of United Nations development programs there are 9 principles of good governance:

a)Community Participation

Every citizen has a voice in making decisions, both directly and through

representatives of institutions and institutions that represent the interests of the community. Participation is built based on indicators of freedom of speech and association constructively.

b)The Rule of Law Supremacy

The second principle of good governance is the rule of law. The legal framework and rules must be fair and be applied indiscriminately to anyone, including laws concerning human rights. Some of the characteristics of the rule of law are the rule of law, legal certainty, responsive law, consistent and non-discriminatory law enforcement and judicial independence.

c)Transparency

Transparency is freedom and open access to information in various institutional processes so that those who need it can easily access it. Information must also be understood and can be monitored. So all government actions and policies must be open and accessible.

d)Responsiveness

Every government institution must serve every party, the responsiveness process carried out by the institution must be directed to serve the parties concerned for the sake of upholding the principles of good governance. In the context of business practice, the company has a moral responsibility to support how good governance can run well in each of its institutions.

e)Consensus Oriented

Consensus oriented, namely acting as a mediator to achieve joint effort. So good governance becomes a bridge between different interests in order to obtain the best choices for community groups, especially in terms of policies and procedures. So any decision must be made through a process of deliberation through consensus.

f)Equality

All community members have the opportunity to improve or maintain their welfare. Equality, namely equality in treatment and service both to men and women in an effort to improve the quality of life.

g)Effectiveness and Efficiency

Effectiveness and efficiency is one of the principles of good governance that all processes and institutions that are directed to produce something are really needed and in accordance with the resources they have so that they produce results according to the needs of the community members. Therefore, good and clean government must also meet the criteria of effective and efficient namely efficient and effective.

h)Accountability

The basis of accountability is the existing legislation, with political commitment to accountability and accountability mechanisms, while supporting instruments are the guidelines for behavior and the performance monitoring system of government administrators and surveillance systems with clear and firm sanctions.

i)Strategic Vision

Strategic Vision is a strategic view in the future in facing various problems. Leaders and public officials must be able to look to the future that will come in broad human development and in line with what is needed to realize these developments.

2.2 Excellent Service

Government administration carried out by government agencies at the central, regional, and in the environment of state-owned or regionally-owned business entities uses the term conception of service to the public in terms of public services that cover administrative services, agreements and public services. In the face of globalization which is full of challenges and opportunities, the state apparatus in this case emphasizes the government apparatus should provide the best service, oriented to the needs and satisfaction of service recipients, so as to increase competitiveness in the delivery of goods and services. The enactment of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 22 of 1999 concerning local government, is expected to have a real and tangible impact on improving services to the community, delegation of authority from the central government to local governments allows the delivery of services

with a bureaucratic path that is more concise and opens opportunities for local governments to innovate in giving and improving service quality.

2.3 Public Satisfaction

The success of service delivery is determined by the level of satisfaction of the service recipient. Service recipient satisfaction will be achieved if the recipient of the service gets the service that is needed as needed and expected. If the service provided is the best service, it can automatically be said that the community will feel satisfied, but if the service provided is not the best service, it is clear that the community will feel disappointed or dissatisfied. Therefore, each service provider must periodically carry out a survey of the community satisfaction index, so that the government as a service provider can know more precisely how the community's response to the services provided, so that any form of public response to the services provided can be a separate evaluation for the government.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types and Nature of Research

This type of research is quantitative descriptive research. According to Sinulingga (2013:31) descriptive research is a type of research that aims to mendandra or describe systematically, factual, and accurate about the facts and properties of a particular object or population. The purpose and purpose of this research is only limited to making an appropriate description, what are the facts and properties of the object without making predictions or finding solutions to the problems that exist in the object. Descriptive research is often referred to as survey research because the data used are collected with interview techniques supported by schedule questions or interview guides. While quantitative research according to Emzir (2009:28) is a research approach that primarily uses the postpositivist paradigm in developing knowledge such as thinking about causation, reduction of variables, hypotheses and

specific questions using measurement and observation and theory testing.

This research is an explanatory research. According to Sugiyono (2012:21) explanatory research is research that intends to explain the position of the variables studied as well as the relationship between one variable and its other variables. Explanation of the position of these variables is done through hypothesis testing.

3.2 Research Location and Time

This research was conducted in Medan Tembung Subdistrict which is located at Jalan Kapten Jamil Lubis No. 107 Medan Postal Code 20223. Telephone (061)7321810. The time of this research was conducted from September 2019 to November 2019.

3.3 Population and Samples

The total population according to adult age group and gender registered in all kelurahans in Medan Tembung Sub-District is 73,105 people.

According to Sugiyono (2012) the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. If the population is large, and researchers may not study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, manpower, and time, then researchers can use samples drawn from that population. Because the population in this study is known to be 73,105 people, so in taking the number of samples the author uses the Slovin formula. Then the numbers of samples in this study were 100 respondents.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis method used in this study is the SEM analysis method with data processing using a partial least square (PLS) computer program version 3.0. PLS model is done by evaluating the measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model). Assessment of measurement models (outer models) aims to test the construct validity and reliability of the instrument. Construct validity test uses convergent validity and discriminant validity method while the reliability test uses compositor reliability and cronbach's

alpha methods. The final result of structural model testing (inner model) and the significance of the model is done using the bootstrap method (non-parametric method) because PLS does not use the assumption of normally distributed data (Hair et al, 2014). Also according to Ghozali (2015) in Puryanto (2015:40) PLS is a powerful analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions. For example, data must be normally distributed and sample does not have to be large.

RESULT

a) Direct Effects

Analysis of direct effects (path coefficients) and indirect effects aims to determine the strength of constructs, both directly and indirectly, namely the direct effect of good governance on excellent service, the direct effect of good governance on public satisfaction and the direct influence of primary service on satisfaction of primary services public. The indirect effect, that is, the effect of good governance on public satisfaction intervened by excellent service. The direct effect (path coefficient) and the indirect can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Direct Effects (Path Coefficients)

Keterangan	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
GG -> KP	0.518	0.519	0.059	8.768	0.000
GG -> PP	0.454	0.454	0.059	7.740	0.000
PP -> KP	0.496	0.493	0.061	8.095	0.000

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

Note: GG (Good Governance), PP (Excellent Service), KP (Public Satisfaction)

The p value of the effect of good governance (GG) on excellent service (PP) (GG -> PP) is 0,000 with a statistical T of 7,740 and the path coefficient is positive. By p value < 0.05 and T statistic > 1.96 and the path coefficient is positive, it is concluded that good governance (GG) has a positive and significant effect on excellent services (PP). This shows that the higher the good governance, the higher the excellent service at the Medan Tembung Sub-District Office. This supports hypothesis 1 in this study so that hypothesis 1 is accepted.

The p value of the influence of excellent service (PP) on public satisfaction (KP) (PP -> KP) is 0,000 with a statistical T of 8.095 and the path coefficient is positive. By p value < 0.05 and T statistic > 1.96 as well as positive path coefficient, it was concluded that excellent service (PP) had a

positive and significant effect on public satisfaction (KP). This shows that the better the excellent service, the higher the public satisfaction, and vice versa. This supports hypothesis 2 in this study so hypothesis 2 is accepted.

The p value of the effect of good governance (GG) on public satisfaction (KP) (GG -> KP) is 0,000 with a statistical T of 8.768 and the path coefficient is positive. By p value < 0.05 and T statistic > 1.96 and the path coefficient is positive, it is concluded that good governance (GG) has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction (KP). This shows that the better good governance, the higher the public satisfaction, and vice versa. This supports hypothesis 3 in this study so that hypothesis 3 is accepted.

b) Indirect Effects

Table 2. Indirect Effects

Keterangan	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
GG -> PP -> KP	0.225	0.223	0.037	6.098	0.000
GG -> PP					
PP -> KP					

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

Note: GG (Good Governance), PP (Excellent Service), KP (Public Satisfaction)

The p value of the indirect effect of good governance (GG) on public satisfaction mediated by excellent service (GG -> PP -> KP) is 0,000 with a statistical T of 6.098 and positive path coefficient. By p value < 0.05 and T statistic > 1.96 and positive path coefficient, it was concluded that Prime Service (PP) can significantly mediate the effect of good governance (GG) on public satisfaction (KP). This supports hypothesis 4 in this study so that hypothesis 4 is accepted.

The above table summarizes the influence between research variables. Direct effect between variables (direct effects) is an effect that occurs based on the results of calculations between research variables. Indirect effects include the presence of intervening variables in the calculation. The

indirect effect is generated from the multiplication between the direct effect of the independent variable on the intervening variable on the dependent variable.

The significance of the estimated parameters provides very useful information about the relationship between the research variables. The basis used in testing hypotheses is the value found in the output results for inner weight (path coefficients). In PLS statistical testing every hypothesized relationship is carried out with the bootstrap method of the sample.

c) Hypothesis Test

Table 3 gives the results of the bootstrapping test from the PLS analysis. Overall hypothesis test results can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Research Hypothesis Testing

No.	Hypothesis	T Statistic	Conclusion
H ₁	Good governance has a positive and significant effect on excellent service.	7,740 > 1,96	Accepted
H ₂	Excellent service has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction.	8,095 > 1,96	Accepted
H ₃	Good governance has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction.	8,768 > 1,96	Accepted
H ₄	Good governance has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction through excellent service.	6,098 > 1,96	Accepted

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Data Processed)

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion in previous chapters, then the conclusions can be drawn are as follows:

- a) Good governance has a positive and significant direct effect on excellent service in The Medan Tembung Sub-District Office.
- b) Excellent service has a positive and significant direct effect on public satisfaction in The Medan Tembung Sub-District Office.
- c) Good Governance has a positive and significant direct effect on public satisfaction in The Medan Tembung Sub-District Office.
- d) Good Governance has a positive effect on public satisfaction through excellent service in The Medan Tembung Sub-District Office.

SUGGESTION

5.2.1 For Medan Tembung Sub-District Office

- a) Regarding good governance which is found in the criticism of clay fields, it should be increased, because based on the results of the description of the variables it is known that the good governance variable which amounts to eight indicators, there are about seven indicators that obtain poor results. As in the indicators "Involving Communities to Provide Input on Complaints Regarding the Service Process" and "Involving Communities for Joint Meeting Activities" with respondents' answers there were those who disagreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed, therefore Medan Tembung Sub-District Office was advised to increase public participation by provide facilities/provide access to the community to convey their problems and further enhance the role of the community to be involved in joint deliberations. Then what needs to be addressed and improved is on the indicators "Every Complaint of Service Applicant Can Be Accountable" and

"Carry Out Tasks Professionally" with the respondent's answers there are those who disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore Medan Tembung Sub-District Office is advised to pay more attention and manage every complaint from the community to improve better services, then it is suggested that Medan Tembung Sub-District better understand their duties and responsibilities, relationships, and relations and focus and be consistent with the work of demilitarization in order to create better services. Furthermore, the results that are less good are the indicators "Not Distinguishing Status of the Applicant in Providing Services" and "Service Implementation Has Been Fairly Performed" with the answers of respondents who disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore Medan Tembung Sub-District Office is advised to improve and improve better services by way of services that are provided more equitably and more equitably for all service applicants such as there is no longer a saying that says "Employees Will Fast Serve, If Already Familiar" but change it all to "Serve the Community Wholehearted and Soul, Without Making Disappointed Society".

b) Related to excellent service in the District of Medan Tembung also needs to be improved, because based on the description of the variables it is known that in the Prima Service variable which amounts to twelve indicators, there are about two indicators that get poor results and one indicator that gets bad results. As an indicator that results are not good that is "Cheap Smiling Attitude During Serving" related indicators such respondents there are respondents who disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore it is recommended that Medan Tembung Sub-District Office an Tembung Sub-District employees to improve the habit of smiling when serving the community, then it is expected that employees in the Medan Tembung Sub-District Office makes smile as a habit in Medan Tembung Sub-District Office during serving the community such as the slogan "Greetings,

Smiles, Sapa" to be the principle in serving the community, thus the community will feel privileged so that the community will be more loyal. Then the indicator that got an unfavorable result was "Greeting When the Petitioner Was at the Service Location" regarding the indicator respondents responded who disagreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed, therefore it was recommended that Medan Tembung sub-district staff improve their habits of wanting to greet service requesters, make the community is like a teenager when they are at the service location by "Greetings, Smiles, and Sapa". Then the indicator that got a poor result was "Saying Gratitude When Completed Serving" related to this indicator respondents answered that they disagreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed, therefore it was suggested that Medan Tembung Sub-District Office employees to be more accustomed to always say thank you when finished serving the service applicant, because in fact it is an excellent service criteria in accordance with the service motive in the District of Medan Tembung.

c) Regarding public satisfaction in the District of Medan Tembung also needs to be improved so that the public feels a higher level of satisfaction, because based on the results of the description of the Public Satisfaction variable consisting of twenty-eight indicators, there are about nine indicators with poor results and one indicator with results that are not well. Indications that get less results are "Satisfied Because Employees Are Always In Place During Service Hours" and "Satisfied Because Employees Do Not Wear Clasps when working hours" related to these indicators respondents' answers were disagreeing, disagreeing and strongly disagreeing, because it was suggested by Medan District employees Tembung further increases discipline, especially so that it is in place during service hours even though no community has yet come, then routinely to supervise and give reprimands if there are employees who violate the discipline. some

respondents answered disagreeing, disagreeing, and strongly disagreeing, therefore it was suggested that Medan Tembung District employees be on time to complete the applicant's documents, such as not promising the applicant that the document would finished a few days, but the promise was not fulfilled. Then the indicators that are not good are "Satisfied Because Service Processes Are Implemented Quickly" and "Satisfied Because Employees Don't Make Long-Waiting Service Applicants" regarding these indicators there are respondents who answer the disapproving, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore Medan Tembung Sub-District Office employees are advised to be more pay more attention to service applicants so that they feel well served, then be aware of their duties as public servants, increase their ability to carry out their duties to be more adequate so that the work process will be carried out quickly, so as to obtain maximum work results. Then the indicators that get poor results "Satisfied Because Employees Calling Petitioners take turns" related to these indicators adpondents who answered disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore Medan Tembung Sub-District Office employees are advised to be more consistent and prudent in serving service applicants, such as I did not prioritize calling for service applicants who had come for business, but who came first came first and vice versa. Then the indicators that get less good results "Satisfied Because the Condition of the Waiting Room Services Feel Comfortable" related to these indicators there are respondents who answered disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore it is recommended that employees of Medan Tembung Subdistrict make more comfortable waiting room conditions, such as adding the number of seats so that no one stands up. The next indication is "Satisfied Because There Are No Wild Charges From Employees" related to this indicator there are respondents who answered disagree,

disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore it is suggested that the leaders of Medan

Tembung Sub-District Office to be more supervising and attentive to their employees, so that employees no longer take advantage of opportunities to take profits by extorting extortion to the community. The next indicator that gets poor results is "Satisfied Because Employees Serve the Same (Not Alternating)" related to these indicators there are respondents who answered disagreed, disagreed, and strongly disagree, therefore MedanTembung Subdistrict employees are advised to be more structured in their work, that is, each position is adjusted to their work, so that there is a form of clarity in serving officers. The last indicator that gets a bad result is "Satisfied Because Employees Serve Politely" related to this indicator adpondents who answered disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, therefore it is suggested that Medan Tembung Sub-District Office employees serve more politely, such as speaking weak gentle, more friendly to every applicant for service, regardless of age. Remember the service motto in Medan Tembung Sub-District Office, one of which is "Excellent Service", so it should provide the best service to make people feel satisfied.

5.2.2 For Future Researchers

Future studies should be able to continue this research by adding research variables or by modifying the research model. Further research can also be carried out by adding research samples so that more analyzed data.

REFERENCES

1. Emzir. 2009. *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan, Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
2. Fitriani, R.D. 2017. *Mewujudkan Good Governance Melalui Pelayanan Publik dalam Era Otonomi Daerah*. Wedana (Jurnal Pemerintahan, Politik, dan Birokrasi), 3 (1), 324-330.
3. Hair, J.F, Jr., G.T.M. Hult, C.M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt. 2014. *A Primer on Partial*

- Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Sage.
4. Puryanto, D. 2015. *Pengaruh Kualitas Fasilitas, Kualitas Pembelajaran dan Lokasi terhadap Keputusan Memilih Jasa Pendidikan di SMP IT Global Insani Islamic School-Bekasi*. Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis STIE YPN, VIII(2), 31-45.
 5. Kotler, Philip and Kevin Lane Keller. 2009. *Manajemen Pemasaran Edisi 12*. Jilid 1. Alih Bahasa: Bob Sabran. Jakarta: Erlangga.
 6. Ridwan, Juniarso and Sodik Sudrajat, Achmad. 2009. *Hukum Administrasi Negara dan Kebijakan Pelayanan Publik*. Bandung: Nuansa.
 7. Santosa, P. 2008. *Administrasi Publik Teori dan Aplikasi Good Governance*. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
 8. Sinulingga, Sukaria. 2013. *Metode Penelitian*. Edisi 3. Medan: USU Press.
 9. Sugiyono. 2012. *Metode Penelitian Administrasi*. Cetakan Ke-20. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- How to cite this article: Sitompul F, Lumbanraja P, Tarmizi HB. Effect of good governance application against public satisfaction with excellent service as an intervening variable in the Medan Tembung sub-district office. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(1): 244-252.
